

SOCIAL MEDIA GUIDE

EURAKNOS

*Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural
Knowledge Innovation Open Source System*

Table of Content

Table of Content.....	2
Introduction	3
1. Style.....	3
2. Content.....	4
3. Tone	5
Presentation of each social media.....	6

Introduction

EURAKNOS has several social media accounts: Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and Instagram. Based on the advice of European Commission, this guide serves to help us to post regularly on social media. It is proposed to know how to post.

To maximise the impact of the EURAKNOS communication, these suggestions will help to create high-quality content. It improves the consistency of posts from different persons on social media, giving general advice on our behaviours. This presentation is divided in three points: the style, the content, the tone. The most important points are underlined.

1. Style

- Minimise the use of abbreviations, except generally recognised acronyms and accepted hashtags.
- Limit the number of technical words that only experts are likely to understand. Instead try to use layman's terms.
- Use visual aids in your tweets as much as possible, and tag relevant handles.

- Keep your posts short, clear and catchy — 3 sentences at most on Twitter.

- Use software to help you avoid typos and grammar mistakes.
- Convey emotions with your posts (but do not go overboard or undermine your content's credibility with excessive hype or clichéd promotional phrasing).

- **Publish content in other languages, to reach local communities.** We can translate up to 10 different languages. This is more important for EURAKNOS than for other projects due to the need to have a large impact.

2. Content

- Before you post, ask yourself if you would be interested in reading this, or clicking the link to know more.
- Vary the content — include a **picture, video, GIF, infographic, link** or poll to enliven the text. The image credit should be put next to the picture.

Illustrating the activities, e.g. the partners

Sharing contents of the project, e.g. a slide from a workshop

Visual content (as above) is very effective as it conveys a lot of information in an appealing, easily digestible way.

- Share information about **your project results** and final products, new papers and scientific publications, events, conferences and training courses, breaking news and hashtags relevant to your project. We can add some deliverables to this – available at <https://euraknos.eu/deliverables>
- Highlight **the project's impacts** and its contribution to society. We can think about having testimonies of the target audience: from the project partners to the end-users.
- Tag appropriate handles, to ensure your content reaches the widest audience possible.

- Make sure everything you post is accurate — nobody wants to follow an unreliable information source!
- Events – keep in mind that live posts or pictures of events may not necessarily be relevant content for people who did not attend. They are more likely interested in the outcomes of such events (minutes, reports, links to presentations and interviews, etc.).

We must share both contents.

3. Tone

- Use appropriate, inoffensive language (this is how you will get responses and stimulate debate).
- Be receptive to your readers' arguments — if you do not agree, defend your position without being rude.
- Gain/maintain credibility by **sharing worthwhile, relevant content** and show respect for other cultures and ideas, online as well as offline.

Presentation of each social media

Twitter is the main network to spread information. Indeed, it is known as a professional media. An agricultural actor can benefit from the influence of EIP-Agri, which gathers a large community.

Twitter is based on short information, because of the word's limits. The goal is to share short information, to be essential in the posts. The idea is to catch the attention of people to attract them on a website, with a more detailed article. The post must include a photo, a video or a link to have an impact on people.

LinkedIn is known to be a platform for professional. Each post is more detailed, the people will care more attention to read than Twitter. To catch attention, it is better to include a photo or a link to each post.

Facebook impacts mainly a large public. It is more difficult to attract a professional public on this platform, even if it is a similar content to Twitter.

Instagram is based on photos and videos. It is the youngest network of this list and is not based on professional exchange. The idea is to improve the presence on this media, but it is difficult to share scientific information on this media.

Source :

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amqa/soc-med-guide_en.pdf
